

FAKE REVIEW DETECTION THROUGH OPINION MINING USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

With the continuous growth of ecommerce systems, online reviews are important one for increasing and decreasing a particular product's sales. Reviews give a platform for people write their own experience about a product. This will helps customers to buy a good product. Today bogus reviews are increased to spoil the reputation of a particular product or increase the sale of a particular product. So detecting fake reviews is the important one. In this research, we used opinion mining for detecting fake reviews by classifying no of positive and negative reviews in the given sample dataset. Especially we use three machine learning algorithms: Bernoulli Naive Bayes, LinearSVC, Logistic Regression.

Keywords: *Fake Reviews, Opinion Mining, Machine Learning, Sentiment Analysis.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In this emerging digital world, people can do anything from their residence through internet. In order to save their time and travelling cost they choose this way. For example we take shopping, today many of the people are not directly wants to buy their necessary products. Due to the popularity and portability of the internet they prefer to buy products from online websites from their place by their smart phone. Online shopping has many facilities like discount offers, cash back, return policy, customer reviews, door delivery etc. especially customer feedback is a crucial one. Customer feedback

would decide the particular product's sale because buyers want to see the reviews of the previous customers before they decide to buy a product. While increasing of online shopping, fake reviews are also increased. Some dishonest people creating spam reviews for marketing their product or damaging the image of a particular product. This will leads to increase the market of an unfair product or reduce the market of a fair product.

In this research, we use opinion mining. Sentiment analysis is another name for opinion mining. Sentiment analysis is one of the popular domain today. Nowadays more researches done on sentiment analysis. It is mainly used to find a sentiment behind the text. This methodology uses machine learning classifiers (Bernoulli Naive Bayes (BernoulliNB), Linear Support Vector Classification (LinearSVC) and Logistic Regression (LR)) to detect positive reviews and negative reviews.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Ahmed M. Elmogy et.al. (2021) compares the performance of several experiments done on a real Yelp dataset of restaurants reviews with several classifiers; KNN, Naive Bayes (NB), SVM, Logistic Regression and Random forest. Also, different language models of n-gram ^[1].

Shilpa yadav et.al. (2021) implemented Fake review detection taken dataset by applying three feature extraction techniques namely CountVectorizer, Ngram model, TfidfVectorizer. The extracted features are

trained and predicted using four machine learning algorithms namely Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, SVM [2].

Deepika Vachane et.al. (2021) developed a new named spam recognition framework, which uses spam highlights for showing review enlightening lists as heterogeneous information structures to configuration spam ID strategy into a gathering of issue [3].

Gyandeep Dowari et.al. (2020) focused on detecting fake product reviews or spam reviews in the sample reviews by checking number of positives, negative and neutral using Opinion Mining and use Spam dictionary to identify the spam words in the reviews. For Text Mining, apply Naïve Bayes classifier and SVM classifier and compare their result that which one is more accurate and on the basis of these algorithms to get the specific results [4].

Elshrif Elmurngi and Abdelouahed Gherbi (2018) analyze online movie reviews using sentiment analysis methods. Five supervised machine learning algorithms are applied to a two various datasets of movie reviews and compare their results to get which one is more accurate than others [5].

Anusha Sinha et.al. (2018) proposed a framework to detect fake product reviews or spam reviews by using Opinion Mining with the help of Decision tree and use Spam dictionary to identify the spam words in the reviews. For Text Mining, apply several algorithms and on the basis of these algorithms get the specific results [6].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this proposed system, text classification and opinion mining methods are used for detecting fake reviews. This methodology contains the following steps:

Data Collection-collecting customer reviews dataset

Data Preprocessing- processing noisy data from the sample dataset to a digestible form. In this process the below steps are followed

1. Tokenization
2. Lower casing
3. Remove short words
4. Remove stop words
5. Lemmatizing

Feature Selection- the processed data can be converted into set of features

Algorithm Selection- Bernoulli Naive Bayes (BernoulliNB), Linear Support Vector Classification (LinearSVC) and Logistic Regression (LR) algorithms are used for sentiment analysis

Detection process- in this process we get no of True Positive, False Positive, True Negative and False Negative from the given dataset.

Results- Finally compares the accuracy of all the 3 algorithms to decide which algorithm is best for finding fake positive and fake negative reviews.

Flowchart

The following figure depicts this methodology

Figure 1: Flowchart of the proposed system

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The following Table 1 shows the Precision, Recall and F1-Score of the three sentiment analysis classifiers used in this research.

Table 1: Precision, Recall and F1-Score of various Classifiers

Class	Classifiers	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
Positive	BernoulliNB	81	79	80
	LinearSVC	82	81	82
	Logistic Regression	83	82	83
Negative	BernoulliNB	80	81	80
	LinearSVC	81	83	82
	Logistic Regression	82	84	83

The following Table 2 displays the accuracy results of Bernoulli Naive Bayes, Linear Support Vector Classification and Logistic Regression classifiers.

As compared to other algorithms Logistic Regression has higher accuracy of 83%.

Table 2: Accuracy of Various Classifiers

Classifiers	Accuracy (%)
Bernoulli Naive Bayes (BernoulliNB)	80
Linear Support Vector Classification (LinearSVC)	82
Logistic Regression (LR)	83

The following Figure 2 shows the graphical representation of the above Table 2.

Figure 2: Comparing accuracy level of 3 algorithms

The below Confusion Matrix Table 3 shows the Number of True Negative, False Positive, False Negative and True positive for each algorithm.

Table 3: Confusion Matrix of all algorithms

Algorithms	True Negative	False Positive	False Negative	True Positive
BNB	39.64%	10.35%	9.47%	40.55%
LinearSVC	40.47%	9.51%	8.64%	41.37%
LR	40.94%	9.05%	8.10%	41.91%

Figure 3: Graphical representation of confusion matrix of all algorithms

In the above Figure 3 clearly depicts Logistic Regression performs well in detecting number of positive and negative reviews in a sample dataset.

V. CONCLUSION

This research proposes 3 sentiment analysis classification algorithms to detect number of positive and negative reviews in the sample dataset. The classification algorithms are Bernoulli Naive Bayes, LinearSVC, Logistic Regression. This methodology is applied to the sample dataset to predict the results. The predictions are done by Bernoulli Naive Bayes, LinearSVC, Logistic Regression algorithms. Finally the accuracy of all the three algorithms is compared. The accuracy comparison will clearly shows that Logistic Regression outperforms from the other classifiers.

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